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मध्य भारती

मानविकी एवं समाजविज्ञान की द्विभाषी शोध-पत्रिका

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राष्ट्रीय शिक्षा नीति-2020 : परिप्रेक्ष्य और परिवर्त्य

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डॉक्टर हरीसिंह गौर विश्वविद्यालय, सागर (म.प्र.)

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प्रकाशित रचनाओं के अभिमत से डॉक्टर हरीसिंह गौर विश्वविद्यालय, सागर या सम्पादकों की सहमति अनिवार्य नहीं है, तथा यहाँ प्रकाशित आलेखों 'प्लेजिअरिज्म' (Plagiarism) सम्बन्धी शुचिता की जिम्मेदारी लेखकों की है।

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ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract

Science and Technology, innovations and inventions have always widened the human edge may this be in any field and financial sector is not an exception. In the current scenario the Artificial intelligence (AI) and Machine learning (ML) undoubtedly turned as an integral part and indispensable from many of those fields, thus catalyzing in the process of development and are bringing political, economic and social transformation in emerging economies. This study explores role of AI in achieving the financial inclusion across selected developing economies. Financial Inclusion is vital for economic development particularly in developing markets, where traditional barriers like limited access to banking infrastructure and inadequate credit assessments exists. AI- based solutions using data analytics, machine learning and automation will be a game- changer, enabling innovative fintech solutions in addressing these challenges that can extend banking services to marginalized populations. Using the World bank's Global Findex data, this paper examines key indicators such as account ownership, digital payment usage and access to credit across emerging countries like India, Kenya, Brazil and China. The analysis makes obvious how AI-enabled fintech applications have harnessed a significant progress in these regions, with certain case studies of AI applications by leading banks and fintech firms. While AI has considerably increased financial access, challenges persist in areas such as digital literacy, regulatory frameworks and privacy concerns. This paper underscores the potential of AI to further financial inclusion while addressing enduring challenges in these developing economies.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Digitalization, Artificial Intelligence

Introduction

In a recently held McKinsey's 21st Global Digital Banking Conference in Barcelona, "Unleashing gen AI: Digital banking in 2024 and beyond", gave a good sense of the changing landscape congregated by more than 280 executives from 150- plus leading financial services institutions. The conference showcased banking tech in action and that of scaling generative AI deployment outcomes. The key takeaways are: primary, that incumbents are getting their act together on digital banking in some dominant new ways; next, they brought technology as their core capability; lastly, the next big challenges could be faced with this new focus on technological capabilities. This event underscores the indispensable and mounting role of AI in financial inclusion and their understanding for an inclusive growth and development.

Financial access eases day to day living, and supports families and businesses plan for long term goals to unexpected emergencies. Financial inclusion allows individuals and businesses have access to useful and affordable financial products and services that meet their needs and ensures transactions, payments, savings, credit and insurance were delivered in a responsible and sustainable way. Financial inclusion is key to equitable economic development and has been acknowledged as an enabler for 7 of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. It is considered as a key spur to reduce extreme poverty and boost shared prosperity. However, in many developing countries, lack of access to formal banking, physical distance and lack of financial literacy, digital literacy are the indispensable barriers hindering this SDG's.

Access to transaction accounts opens up the corridor for broader financial inclusion, where individuals can make financial transactions more efficiently and safely. It also enables participation in digital economy and is a critical building block for digital development. As account holders, people can avail other financial services ranging from credit access to insurance, to setup and expand businesses, invest in education or health, to mitigate risk and weather financial shocks. This inclusion helps in improving the overall quality of their lives.

The COVID-19 crisis also reinforced the need and augmented the urgency for digital financial services (DFS) highlighting the increased importance of digital financial inclusion. Digital financial services provide secure, low cost and contactless financial tools to individuals and businesses and also critical in reaching undeserved and vulnerable population. Digital financial inclusion reaches financially excluded and undeserved population by deploying cost saving digital means. It provides formal financial services and needs additionally ensuring these are responsibly delivered at a cost affordable to customers and sustainable for providers. As the G20 is committed to advance financial inclusion worldwide it reaffirmed to put this into operation the G20 High-Level Principles for Digital Financial Inclusion.

The key features of digital finance comprise quick authentication of identity, compatible use of mobile devices and real time payment services. At the same time can be applied to hundreds of millions of customers even for low value transactions which were undreamed of just a decade ago. Recent facts have once again exposed those digital technologies is a powerful tool to overcome those traditional barriers and boost access to the banking and financial system. Much has already been achieved: according to Global Findex data in India alone, nearly half a billion adults opened bank accounts between 2011 and 2017.

Currently technological advancements like AI coupled with Machine Learning, Big Data, Industry 4.0 and Internet of Things (IoT) have ushered in a revolution in the financial sector with AI being in the forefront. Machines are inclined to think, create and react to data with the help of AI. AI mimics human intelligence by enabling machines to learn, predict and make decisions based on data (Hassani et al., 2020; Truby et al., 2020). These developments are key for intensifying financial inclusion ensuring that undeserved population gain access to banking, credit and other financial services.

According to World Bank data 2022, the largest unbanked populations are found in China (224 million), India (191 million), Pakistan (99 million), and Indonesia (97 million). Women account for 980 million unbanked individuals globally, with 132 million in China, 109 million in India, 56 million in Pakistan, and 47 million in Indonesia. AI and ML are rapidly evolving, offering

transformative potential to overcome financial exclusion, especially for these regions in this developing world.

The central challenge in increasing financial inclusion is integrating populations into a country's formal financial system. Economic growth, investment, and entrepreneurship are stunted when financial transactions occur outside the formal sector, often at the mercy of informal money lenders. Then the other challenge is to retain individuals in this formal system through continuous advancements and satisfactory performance. By enabling digital financial infrastructures through AI, the significant gaps in inclusion between genders, income groups, and education levels can be bridged. AI offers predictive analytics, automated decision-making, and mobile banking, which make financial services more accessible to underserved populations (Truby et al., 2020).

Transformation from digitalization to AI- driven approaches

The transition from traditional followed by mere digitalization and then to AI in financial inclusion, can be traced over recent two decades occurring in several key phases. Before digitalization (pre- 2000's) financial systems in developing countries were traditional highly dependent on physical banking infrastructures, inaccessible to rural and undeserved areas. The early digitalization observed in 2000-2010 with the advent of mobile banking and fintech platforms, offered basic financial services to underserved population facilitating millions of unbanked to open bank accounts.

AI emergence in financial inclusion observed in 2010-2015, by 2010 AI and big data analytics were being adopted in the areas of analyzing financial behaviors and improving access to credit for unbanked population. AI used for assessing creditworthiness in peer-to-peer lending and crowd funding platforms which is an aid for expanding financial access. AI driven financial inclusion is a glimpse today, since 2015 rapid and continuous changes till date in the technologies revolutionized the financial sector and still updating on day-to-day basis. Credit scoring done by using mobile usage patterns and social media behavior, AI driven fraud detection systems enhanced security boosting the financial inclusion in regions such as South Asia and Africa.

Developing Countries Context

According to World bank's Global Findex data, financially included people in the world are about 76% and most of the unbanked population is in developing countries. These developing countries face unique challenges large unbanked population, physical distance, inadequate banking infrastructure and regulatory issues. However, there's a drastic improvement in the increase of account holders, digital payments and access to credit services observed in few developing countries. The intervention of digitalization, adoptions of AI & ML technologies, through mobile banking, AI- driven micro financing, and various digital financial solutions enhanced the inclusive growth. This is very much evident from the following table extracted from Global Findex data.

Table.1: Financial inclusion & Cross-Country comparison using three indicators:

Country	Year	Account (% age 15+)	Made or received a Digital payment	Borrowed to start, operate, or expand a farm or business (% age 15+)
India	2011	35%		
	2014	53%	22%	9%
	2017	80%	29%	7%
	2021	78%	35%	
Kenya	2011	42%		
	2014	75%	69%	24%
	2017	82%	79%	20%
	2021	79%	78%	
Brazil	2011	56%		
	2014	68%	59%	3%
	2017	70%	58%	4%
	2021	84%	77%	
China	2011	64%		
	2014	79%	49%	7%
	2017	80%	67%	5%
	2021	89%	86%	

Source: World Bank, Global Findex Database (2022)

The extracted Global Findex database offers financial inclusion statistics for four developing countries- India, Kenya, Brazil and China over multiple years. There are more than 1200 indicators for assessing financial inclusion, but for this study three financial inclusion indicators: Account ownership, usage of digital payments and access to credit i.e., borrowing for business purposes are chosen as they are critical factors for inclusive growth and economic development in developing countries.

Table.1 shows a significant progress in financial inclusion across India, Kenya, Brazil and China, predominantly in account ownership. Out of four countries India witnessed a rapid and drastic growth in account ownership from 35% to 80% from 2011-2017, due to initiatives like the Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana. However, account ownership slightly declined to 78% in 2021, due to cyber security concerns although indicating a potential plateau. Kenya and China, on the other hand, had a remarkable increase in account ownership, mainly driven by digital platforms like Alipay and WeChat Pay in China and mobile money systems like M-Pesa in Kenya. Brazil, in terms of account ownership shown a steady growth to 84% by 2021, viewing a consistent effort towards financial inclusion.

Across all the four countries, there's a rise in digital payments with Kenya and China leading the way and 2021 data project, 78% of adults in Kenya and 86% in China were using digital modes for making or receiving payments, showcasing a strong headship in transitioning towards cashless economies. Conversely, all the countries exhibit a relatively low borrowing for entrepreneurial purposes, except for Kenya, where the borrowings declined from 24% to 20% for

business purposes from the year 2014 to 2017. Regardless of these improvements in access to bank accounts and digital services, access to credit for business purposes remains a challenge, trigger the requirement for further better inclusive financial policies to encourage entrepreneurship and economic development in developing countries for a speedy convergence with developed nations.

This study discusses the call for AI adoption in the financial sector to achieve financial inclusion. Moreover, the usage of ML techniques has also been highlighted. This current study aims to explore the role of AI in Financial inclusion in developing countries through literature review and case studies. The second objective is to underscore the effect of transformation from mere digitalization to adoption of AI & ML technologies for achieving optimal financial inclusion in a country. Based on these objectives, this research addresses the following question: What are the AI technologies adopted in developing countries for achieving financial inclusion? What is the impact of these AI & ML adoptions for financial inclusion on the economic developments in the selected developing countries?

This is theoretical research and focuses on reviewing the existing literature, and analyzing the role of AI in financial inclusion through case studies and reports of research platforms like McKinsey, Global Findex data, and World Bank Financial Inclusion.

AI in Financial Inclusion: Case studies from Developing Countries

India

India's Aadhaar Biometric system an initiative launched in 2009, is a critical tool for direct benefits transfer and financial inclusion. The process of opening bank accounts is simplified, particularly for underserved populations, by offering a unique biometric ID minimizing transaction costs (D'Silva et al., 2019). The e-KYC (Know Your Customer) verification in the banking process can onboard customers quickly and efficiently. The Unified Payments Interface (UPI), launched in 2016 by NPCI, has revolutionized the payment ecosystem, enabled seamless real-time money transfers, and facilitated small-scale entrepreneurship (D'Silva et al., 2019). In addition, Digi Locker and E-Sign have made document management handier by enabling digital storage and e-signatures, further aiding financial inclusion. An AI-driven platform YONO Launched by SBI in 2017, is a unified banking process that integrates multiple platforms of financial services with investments and shopping. Paytm marked a considerable leap in financial inclusion in the year 2017 though launched as a wallet in 2010. In the year 2018 HDFC and ICICI implemented AI-coupled credit scoring tools for targeting underserved populations. These AI-driven credit assessments, improved financial access for millions of individuals previously an exclusion from the formal banking system (World Bank, 2022).

Through all these key initiatives India observed tremendous growth in its digital financial infrastructure. Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana (PMJDY), Aadhaar, and Unified Payments Interface collectively lead to an expansion in financial access, and enhanced service delivery fostering economic inclusion. Over 500 million new bank accounts were opened under PMJDY in the years 2014-2022, facilitating direct benefit transfers and reducing leakages in welfare distribution. At the same time, the usage of UPI empowered small businesses especially in rural

areas. There's a surge in digital transactions surpassed 10 billion transactions per month by 2022. The establishments of MUDRA Micro Units Development and refine Agency and AI based credit scoring tools improved the credit access facilities for underserved segments, disbursed over 18 trillion INR in loans to micro and small enterprises. Over 1.2 billion citizens anchored by Aadhaar, a unique digital identity improved the ecosystem enabled integrating the identity, payments, investments and data sharing. Technological advancements like e-KYC, Digi Locker and Esign lead to a low cost, paperless on boarding banking process could avail financial services more quickly and efficiently. Though issues around data privacy, these advancements have notable improvements in financial inclusion minimizing exclusion errors, laying foundations for a robust digital infrastructure and a regulatory system that underpins India's growth and economic empowerment.

Kenya

Kenya's M-Pesa, launched in 2007 by Safaricom is an instrument for advancing financial inclusion and has become significant in Kenya's success stories. In 2015 through partnerships like KCB M-Pesa enabled users to transfer money through mobile phones without the need of bank accounts. with the advent of this millions of Kenyans could access financial services particularly in rural areas (Jack & Suri, 2014). The low-cost accessibility, designed for feature phones, this platform has made it easily and widely accessible. The adoption of AI-based credit scoring has further expanded access to microloans, encouraging small businesses and individuals to easily access much-needed credit. By 2016, AI and ML technologies integration to assess creditworthiness greatly benefited the unbanked. In 2018, additionally block chain trials in microfinance aimed to improve transparency and efficiency in Kenya's financial services. Since 2022, with a continuous advancement in adopted AI technologies in Kenya lead to an implementation of a national digital ID system. The digital credit providers in Kenya are now regulated by the central bank to build a strong regulatory system and robust digital infrastructure.

The initiatives like M-Pesa and partnership with KCB in Kenya revolutionized financial inclusion, resulting over 90% of adults could access mobile services, driving SME growth and 33% contribution to Kenya's GDP by 2019. There's shift from informal economy and consequentially in poverty reduction because of easy access to savings, loans and remittances. according to 2016 study 2% of households being lifted from poverty. An easy access to loans and insurance enhanced the productivity in agricultural sector, since remittances through M-Pesa has become a vital source of household income.

Brazil

Brazil's financial inclusion backed by Various digital initiatives, after 2015 Banco do Brasil expanded its digital services, while Nubank, launched in 2013, became popular with its digital only model providing financial services for unbanked and rural communities in Brazil. Pix Payment System, launched by the Central Bank of Brazil in 2020, enabled instant, 24/7 payments, greatly enhancing access to financial services for the unbanked and rural communities. This initiative had a tremendous transformative effect on financial inclusion, reducing unbanked population from 29% in 2014 to 16% in 2021. Furthermore, the Caixa Tem

app launched in 2020, was instrumental in distributing social benefits and emergency aid during the COVID-19 Pandemic.

Brazil's digital banking initiatives and real-time payment services boosted greater consumer spending, especially among lower-income individuals thus resulted in a significant contribution to financial inclusion and economic development. By 2022, Nubank issued loans to over 40 million people (no prior formal credit) encouraging credit access to micro and small enterprises. The Pix payment system launched in 2020, has further boosted economic formalization, with over 100 million people and 8 million businesses using it by 2022, increased tax revenue. Over 60 million underserved Brazilians benefited an emergency aid during COVID-19 pandemic, this helped to mitigate the impact on low-income households' group further reducing poverty in the country.

China

In China with the advent of digital platforms like Alipay and WeBank by Alibaba Group in 2004 China's financial landscape took a new shape. These transformations through digital innovations by Alibaba Group laid to offer AI-driven micro loans and wealth management services, Tencent introduced WeBank in 2014 which is country's first digital only bank, enabling AI powered banking solutions for individuals and small businesses. Around 2015, QR code payments launched by WeChat Pay and Alipay revolutionized the transactions in both rural and urban areas. China is in forefront in adopting AI technologies, by 2016 major banks like ICBC started using AI for risk assessments in loan process and customer service enhancements. By 2017, China started exploring blockchain for cross-border financial services laying foundations for technologies in this finance sector.

China largely through Alipay and WeChat Pay enabled over 80% (by 2020) of adults to have formal accounts driving for financial inclusion, both the platforms Alipay and WeBank has become an integral part to its broader economic growth strategy. Platforms like WeBank provided credit to over 20 million small businesses (by 2021), fuelling SME-driven growth contributing around 60% to China's GDP. However, on the other hand digital payment platforms encouraged consumer spending boosting the participation in the formal economic. China observed an incredible access to savings and investments products through digital platforms like Ant Fiancial's Yu'e Bao further promoting wealth accumulation among ordinary citizens. AI driven financial services reached rural population, simultaneously supporting farmers to invest in agriculture and thus reducing poverty, during 2015- 2020 these initiatives are vital and made significant contributions to China's poverty alleviation.

China's digital payment and financial services platforms not only enabled greater financial inclusion but also helped bridge the gap between urban and rural populations, ensuring equitable access to financial resources. Moreover, the rapid development of these platforms spurred innovation within the fintech sector, creating new opportunities for economic growth and contributing to China's rise as a global leader in digital finance.

Opportunities and Challenges

AI-driven microfinance platforms, block chain technologies-based transactions, real time credit scoring behavioral models have an immense potential to revolutionize the financial services landscape in developing economies (Mhlanga,2020). As, AI offers enormous opportunities for financial inclusion by providing scalable solutions which are low cost and also enhancing financial literacy in these developing countries. In spite of these digital technologies and advances, around 1.7 billion people remain unbanked, with virtually all unbanked individuals living in developing economies and women are about 1 billion unbanked globally and unbanked individuals are poorest 40% of households indicating additional developments for digital financial inclusion means to bridge this gap.

Despite these advances, few challenges still persist. Data privacy, cyber security risks, regulatory structure hurdles and inadequate digital literacy are critical barriers hindering financial inclusion in developing countries. One more concern is Algorithmic bias, as AI models may inadvertently emphasize existing inequalities in access to credit and financial services (Fazal et al., 2023). Data protection and cyber risks are serious and costly, according to Business Today, 2021 report more than 80 million Indian users were affected by data breaches. According to IBM estimates 2021, average cost of data breach in India amounted to USD2.2 million. Data breaches in2021 included Air India, domino's, Facebook, Mobikwik and Upstox exposing users names, mobile numbers and even bank accounts, passport and Aadhaar data (Internet freedom Foundation, 2021).

Policy Implications and Recommendations

Digital access in India remains limited, per 100 inhabitants only 54 have mobile broadband subscriptions whereas the global median is 79 and the median of emerging market economies is 80 with wide inequalities of access within the country. Despite significant progress in technology, digital literacy remains low in developing countries, specifically India which has become a barrier to DPI-based solutions. Digital literacy is “the ability of individuals and communities to understand and use digital technologies for meaningful actions within life situations” (NIELIT, 2022). Thus, it requires individuals to be capable of using smartphones, computers and accessing the internet. Developing countries like India need to build a robust regulatory framework to fully harness AI's potential for financial inclusion, governments and regulators in developing countries should strive to address data protection, algorithmic fairness, and infrastructure development. To foster innovations and enhance digital literacy and financial infrastructure Public-private partnerships should be encouraged and provide resources for.

Conclusion

The world is with ever-evolving financial landscape, and the integration of Generative AI (Gen AI) into the banking system holds transformative promise for driving innovations, efficiency, and financial inclusion. Similar to the role of smartphones in revolutionizing the entire business ecosystems, gen AI is set to reshape the financial sector by blending advanced analytics and personalized services more accessible. Banks that foster integration between technical talent and business leaders are more likely to develop scalable gen AI solutions that create measurable

value. (McKinsey article). This is very much evident from the case studies of India, Kenya, Brazil and China weighing the prominent role of AI-driven solutions for augmenting the financial access to underserved population. However, the adoption of gen AI tools though swift, accompanied with certain challenges.

Talent being a crucial factor in this digital transformation, signaling the need to build and expand AI expertise. Institutions with robust AI teams are better positioned to integrate emerging AI skills such as data base curation and prompt engineering, while others may face notable challenges in utilizing their capabilities. At the same time, regulatory concerns, data privacy and digital literacy hindering adoption of AI's full potential in promoting financial inclusion.

As the role of AI in the financial sector is inevitable and continues to grow, developing countries need to address these challenges to ensure inclusive and equitable deployment of AI based solutions. Further research should focus on the barriers to explore AI's potential in reducing financial exclusion. Banks can unlock new opportunities and help to shape the future of finance and their economies by strategically adopting and navigating the complexities of gen AI.

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